

PECULIAR FEATURES OF MODERN UZBEK PROSE (ON THE EXAMPLE OF U.HAMDAM'S STORY "TULIP")

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ABSTRACT

Modern Uzbek literature becomes diverse, more daring in the choice of form and style. However, with the acquisition of creative freedom, the possibility of pluralism of opinions, there is a danger of the appearance of mediocre production. Uzbek literature of the 20th century absorbed both the national-epic traditions of artistic comprehension of being, and the neo-mythological ways of creating a textual world model, and the existential principle as one of the features of the modernist type of artistic consciousness. The trend of in-depth metaphorization and symbolization of the text, indicated already in the 90s, in order to create a certain, axiologically given, psychological atmosphere in the works of U. Hamdam and other writers of Uzbek short stories of the end of the twentieth century can be predicted as one of the dominant ones in the development of Uzbek literature in the first quarter of the twenty-first century. The paper discusses the interpretations, critiques, evaluations of modern Uzbek writer's novels with the plot-compositional and ideological-thematic structures in the work of U. Hamdam "Tulip" ("Lola").

Introduction. Contemporary writers are looking for and suggesting ways to overcome a new drama of our time: "nature and man live different lives". But the philosophical and ethical prose of U. Hamdam and other artists requires the reader to deeply penetrate into its complex structure. So, in connection with U. Hamdam we can recall two traditional motives of literature: the legend about the original harmonic structure of the natural world order and the story about the imperfection of the modern world.

It is possible to catch a new meaning of modern prose, to see its inherent regularities in the seemingly chaotic interweaving of the paths of modern literature, as G. Belaya proved, subject to inseparable attention to the philosophical, ethical and artistic side of prose, with confidence in the artistic world of modern literature. [1.126]

In Uzbek literature, the relationship between man and nature has always revealed the foundations of the social worldview, and today, we can conclude, the problem of “man and nature” is “a sign of its time”.

Discussion. The period of independence of Uzbek prose is characterized by ideological and artistic innovations and changes. Examination of the human psyche, responsiveness to current socio-political changes of the time is one of the most important features of today's literature. The study of the peculiarities, achievements and shortcomings of the latest examples of Uzbek novels with almost a century of creative experience is one of the current issues of literary criticism. The work of Ulug'bek Hamdam, along with the works of other talented Uzbek prose writers, is in the spotlight of literary critics. The attitude to U. Hamdam's works was first of all reflected in the literary-critical articles. It has been several years since Ulugbek Hamdam's novel “Lola” (“Tulip”) was published. The story “Tulip” (“*Lola*”) by Uzbek writer Ulug'bek Hamdam leads a reader to the deep imaginative world by its title and the gist. From a-time-reading the reader may not comprehend the overall meaning of the story. But it is clear that as the name of story shows this story is about a type of flower “Tulip”. Tulip grows in mountainous areas. So, the background scene of story is a peak a mountain with only a tulip, which serves a nuances and enigmatic metaphor for things like remoteness, loneliness, somehow magic and fatal. The story is filled with all these nuances, which also pervades a reader's ambitious character, his all thoughts and even wishes.

When we observe the work of Ulugbek Hamdam, we encounter the spiritual changes that take place in the life of the protagonist. Ulug'bek Hamdam did not name the character. He only tried to show two different views of a hero, before seeing the tulip at the peak of the mount and after seeing it. So, a hero had totally different views about why so many people are trying to climb the hill, why they are sacrificing them. It is clear from the meaning of the story that a person should not think and decide before knowing the exact reason. A character of a story described as a person who never stops to step forward until he achieved his goal. The story describes the social environment, the relationship between the individual and society in a wide range. The fate of their people, the complex process going on in their psyche, is artistically explored from different angles.

The writer is a plant of ordinary nature - Lola burns with love, strives for life in the story, the hero climbs the rocks to achieve the goal inside, he sees countless people there, he witnesses that people are all striving for the same goal, he also survives among countless people and everyone strives. While scrambling to reach the destination, the symbols and metaphors here come to the world and complete the plot of three realities in the story. He witnesses that all people are striving towards the same goal. He is also passing through countless people and reaching the desired destination they scratch. The symbols and metaphors here come to the world and realize the Supreme Truth of people's way of life, goals and professions. It seems that it is expressed in a concise way. The plot of three realities in the story completes.

The first story: The writer-narrator introduces the reader to the legendary smallpox - Lola introduces people who are striving. This is how people love tulips. They push each other and fall towards the abyss and die. A person without a goal does not exist. Everyone has one in their lifetime explaining the coming to realize the goal on the example of different destinies.

The rock and the one trying to cling to it is the work of someone else. No one even answers anyone's questions. Everyone is there runs for his goal, strives. The great love and affection inside is from Lola - nothing else is available. The writer is telling a story in the language of symbols in his unrealistic story; the hero addresses God, the holy Kaaba and his people. Tell others that you should live according to the great blessing of intellect and thinking it turns out that it consists of meaning.

The second event: the hero of the story realizes his true purpose. He draws conclusions from the mistakes of others. He learns the behavior and methods of climbing to the top - Lola. He was asking others questions, but now the answer to the question comes out by itself. Through reflection, observation and discussion understands his real purpose: "As for me, I looked up and saw nothing but countless people and their chaotic movements. Then, when I moved away from the rock, I repeated: Lola!.. Involuntarily, I remembered the image of the Kaaba and millions of people rushing to it from all directions. Lola was like the sun, and the rest are satellites - a propeller around it..." (*"Men bo'lsam yuqoriga qarab, sanoqsiz odamlardan, ularning betartib harakatlaridan o'zga hech vaqoni ko'rmadim. Keyin qoyadan andak uzoqlashdimda, takror boqdim: Lola!..Yodimga beixtiyor Ka'ba va unga ilinj bilan chor tomondan oshiqib-ko'pchib kelayotgan million-million odamlar surati tushdi. Lola misli quyosh edi-yu qolganlar yo'ldosh - uning atrofida parvona..."*) [2] The most characteristic point of the story unfolds here. Lola - Kaaba in the form of Narrator's speech creates a polyphonic speech and has various addresses Lola is the one and only destination of people coming from places there is a so-called flower, how many people need to grow it to fail is life! Here, the writer puts a huge love in the heart of the hero, after it he realizes his exact goal. "I gave them up before my thoughts matured: after all, Lola spells me... only me! It seems that it has turned away from the rest, after all, it is paying attention only to me, it is inviting me to its presence! Oh, if it is not so attractive, if my heart is not so full of love!.. If it chooses me among so many people, then it knows that I can reach it without getting hurt, and I will be able to do it!"

"Mulohazalarim pishib yetilmayoq ulardan voz kechdim: axir lola meni... faqat meni imlayotir! Qolganlardan yuz o'girganga o'xshaydi, axir mengagina e'tibor berayotir, meningina huzuriga chorlayotir! Oh, u bunchalar jozibali bo'lmasa, yuragim bunchalar to'lib-toshmasa!.. Shuncha odamning orasidan meni saylab oldimi, demak, oldiga shikast yemay yuksala olishimni biladi va men bu ishning uddasidan chiqaman!" [2]

The third event: In the story, this reality makes the hero from aimlessness - prepares for serious tests towards the goal. Climbing countless rocks, annihilation of people, unrealistic interpretation of the story deepens. Only one hero goes towards his goal. To the top no matter how many hardships he faced on his way out, he was pushing him inside. There is a Higher Purpose! There are people on all the roads leading to this destination falling down. No one has anything to do with anyone else. Such a cry and the hero of the story has strong self-confidence to survive among the ravages is hungry Faith is because many people have not been able to define their goals correctly in life. Because of his fragility and hopelessness about the future, he broke half way, and was happy it is destined to be. How many people's unhappiness is due to not thinking about the past and they suffer because they did not draw conclusions from their mistakes. Such the problem that caused the suffering was actually the aimless road. The writer brings out this issue: "Whatever a person does strive for perfection?"

What will he do to reach the destination safely?" For the question, the writer perceives Lola as a flower with a great destination. Therefore, the original idea is embodied in the person himself. "Sweet dreams are good, but they start to prevent me from reaching my goal, and my effort increases. I will pull myself together and give my energy spent on dreams to climb the pass. Now my mind, my body, my soul—my whole being—will come together, and I WILL cross the dangerous peak, albeit with difficulty! Hey, I'm the winner! Alhamdulillah! I jump to the sky without stopping on the rock conquered by joy. I finally get tired and sleep there hugging the rocks...dreaming." *"Shirin xayollar yaxshi-yu, lekin maqsadga yetishimga xalaqit bera boshlaydilar, mashaqqatim ortadi. O'zimni qo'lga olaman-da, orzularga xarjlanayotgan kuchimni-da dovonni oshishga beraman. Endi aql-u hushim, tan va jonim – butun borlig'im birlashadilar va men qiynalib bo'lsa-da xavfli cho'qqini oshib O'TAMAN! Hayhot, g'olibman! Alhamdulillah! Sevinchdan zabt etilgan qoya ustida to'xtamay osmonga sakrayman. Nihoyat charchab, o'sha yerda toshlarni quchoqlab uxlayman... tush ko'raman."* [2]

Tulip is a symbol of human goals. It is in everyone's life indicates the harmony of faith and profession, which is considered important. So, U. Hamdam in the image of a single tulip to the countless problems facing humanity, to the changes taking place in the psyche of people, to their delusions, tried to find answers to his losses, sorrows and joys. Abstract and a mode of syncretic imagery, condensing the epic scene. The result is clear in the story an important sentence begins to appear to the reader. Already Lola's it turns out that it is true that everyone lives in the ideal level in their hearts.

Conclusion. It is well known to both readers and literary critics: Ulugbek Hamdam is one of the most prolific and versatile artists of the independence period. He has done considerable work in the fields of prose, poetry, and literary criticism. While the writer and literary critic Ulugbek Hamdam is known for his modernist research in the field of poetry, he boldly introduces hermeneutic, psychoanalytic methods into his literary studies. Although at first glance, Ulugbek Hamdam's prose works - short stories and novels - seem to be written in the traditional way, they are marked by a semantic renewal. In his prose works, Ulugbek Hamdam examines more the inner world of man. Its protagonists come face to face with their own inner world more than the outer world. The story "Lola" ("Tulip"), which served as an object for this review, is also one of the best examples of modern Uzbek literature. Examining them only in terms of spiritual and moral values, the spiritual image of the individual shows that. Generally, Ulugbek Hamdam in his stories discusses not only inner thoughts of character, but also the most important issues of human life in general, which are of great importance for all periods. The truth is expressed that man always went forward although there is a big threat in front of him. It means that human being should not live according to other's opinions, should make independent decisions.

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